

Assignment on Columbia Gazetteer of the World

Course Name: - Masters of Library and Information Sciences

Subject Name: - Information Sources & Services (Practice)

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Evaluation on the basis of following factors

- *Authority.*
- *Introduction.*
- *Scope.*
- *Treating of Sources.*
- *Arrangement.*
- *Format.*
- *Drawbacks.*
- *Conclusion.*
- *References.*

Authority:

<i>Title</i>	→ Columbia Gazetteer of the World.
<i>Editor</i>	→ Saul B. Cohen.
<i>Publisher</i>	→ Columbia University Press (New York)
<i>Edition</i>	→ I st Ed.- 1998, II nd Ed.- 2008
<i>Contributor</i>	→ Scholars & Experts.
<i>Language</i>	→ English
<i>Volume</i>	→ 3

Introduction:

The definition of the term Gazetteer, when used in a geographical sense, is a "geographical index or dictionary." Gazetteers include brief descriptions along with the listings of places or physical/cultural features. More extensive gazetteers include brief descriptions along with the listings. The comprehensive gazetteer, however, is an encyclopedia of geographical places and features, and this Gazetteer of the World is such an encyclopedia. The Columbia Gazetteer of the World serves also as a unique guide to the ways in which names offer insight into the political, cultural, religious, and aesthetic meanings that people ascribe to particular environments, and in which the values of places change. Most articles have details on where the place is located, its dimensions and borders, and information on economic activities, demographics, history, and former or alternate names and different spellings and pronunciations.

Scope:

The Gazetteer scope is international where the entries include information on many of the following: demography, physical geography, political boundaries, industry, trade, and service activities, agriculture, cultural, historical, and archaeological points of interest, transportation lines, longitude, latitude, and elevations, distance to relevant places, pronunciations, official local government place-names and spellings. The entries here show the input of specialist intimately familiar with a wide variety of sources. The length of entries varies from a brief notation on a small village to an essay on a country or region. The overriding goal was to provide maximum coverage of places and features, while achieving a balanced profile of each country.

Treatment:

This large-scope gazetteer is a one-stop encyclopaedia which provides information about places i.e., information includes different national environment, area size, political administrative framework and cultural significance. The 1998 Gazetteer had 163,000 entries. This revised edition (2008) adds some 7,000 new ones, with many revisions to existing entries. The revised gazetteer provides us with the addition of information about physical features, natural disasters, transportation advances, city development, military bases, technology, conflicts and peace. Historical population figures are also given for selected places and also there is Interlinked glossary of geographic and geological terms. The entries have been continually updated in the online edition by 150 editorial board members and research staff. The information has been selected, arranged, classified and interpreted to provide an up-to-date authoritative reference work of value to librarians, academic researchers, students, writers, people in industry and government, travellers, and all others for whom places hold fascination,

and who require reliable data about them. Pronunciation of places name in the Columbia Gazetteer of the World appears in parentheses next to place names. Capital letters are used to indicate the stressed syllable.

Arrangement:

The Columbia Gazetteer of the World is an authoritative A to Z encyclopedia of geographical places and features. Entries are arranged here in alphabetical order. Information given in 3 volumes.

- Volume 1 - Covers countries from A to G
- Volume 2 - Covers countries from H to O
- Volume 3 - Covers countries from P to Z

The alphabetical list of place names is for students, academic researchers, travellers and anyone interested in factual data about places anywhere in the world as presented below in figure.

Format:

This Gazetteer is available in both the formats print as well as online.

➤ Print version

The printed one has hardcover binding and is in three volumes. The total no. of pages is 4424 and is of good quality. Each book page is in three columns. The dynamism of the world system since World War II is graphically illustrated by changed names for both renewed and pre-existing places. The figures of the most recent complete census have been presented in a very Lucid way.

➤ Online Version

In the Gazetteer Online, there are tools for reorganizing that information and extracting it for different uses. These are **Quick Search** - Quick Search allows you to search either just place-name entry headings or the full-text of Gazetteer articles. This place name entry search is a default search. **Advanced Search** - Advanced Search offers powerful tools to locate very specific lists of Gazetteer entries using a variety of metadata information about those places. **Browse** - The Browse feature allows you to navigate through the complete A to Z list of Gazetteer articles or jump to a particular letter group or to articles that begin with specific letters. **Website** - <http://www.columbiagazetteer.org/main/Home.html>. This is also available online since 2001 and in CD-ROM (July, 12, 2000). Search results are downloadable in both Excel and XML formats.

Drawbacks:

The absence of place maps and regional maps is a disadvantage.

Conclusion:

The Columbia Gazetteer of the World is an encyclopaedia of geographical places and features. It is highly recommended for all academic medium-sized to large public and high school libraries and by geographic scholars. Numerous city name changes also reflect in this gazetteer. Such changes reflect the symbolic importance of place-names in nation building and, in the shaping, or reshaping of national values. This gazetteer is highly recommended for all academics and medium-sized to large public and high-school libraries. It is enormously useful, 24/7 access to current authoritative, geographic information.

Reference:

[1] <http://www.columbiagazetteer.org/main/Home.html>

[2] <https://cup.columbia.edu/reference/gazetteer>

[3] <https://archive.org/details/columbiagazettee02cohe/page/n1/mode/2up>